

COLLABORATIVE DESIGN STRATEGY: KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE FOR ROOF DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

In the (Dutch) Building Industry sub optimal use of knowledge by participants during the design phase causes damage and failure costs, as well as it hinders innovative sustainable solutions. Therefore a design tool was developed to support design knowledge exchange between different design team members. Based on experiments in the period of 2006-2009 a workshop method was developed to support professionals, architects, installers and roofers, in collaborative design teams to share, use and develop collectively knowledge for innovative roofs. The set up of the final collaborative design workshop is explained as well as some results are discussed.

Keywords: Collaborative design, morphological overview, sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Building design is changing, sustainability (Profit, People, Planet) has become an important factor of all decisions including building sustainability as key drivers in architectural design. Also there is a move from prescriptive project-briefs in favor of more performance-orientated design (Holzer 2009). The development of rational methods grew into the Design Methodology movement of 1960's (Cross 2001), culminating and effectively ending as far as architecture is concerned with the early work of Christopher Alexander (1964, 1971). However the need for more rational approaches is strongly felt nowadays by the architectural profession. All this leads to growing need for a intens cooperation between architects and other building designers, however as stated by Holzner (2009) collaboration between architects, engineers, construction managers and owners is difficult as each group has different world views and different modes of practice that are almost incompatible with each

other (Kalay 1998). One mode of practice (Holzer 2009), applied by specialists such as engineers, is dependent on precise problem and goal definitions before they can start to search for solutions, whereas architects - who apply a mode of practice through discovery - are often not capable of "defining desired effects until the design process is well on the way." (Kalay 1998).

Conventionally, architects are somewhat tardy when inviting engineers to join their projects. However by only introducing consulting engineers to participate in the later stages of the design process, engineers are commonly assigned a merely fixing role. This provides little opportunity for creative engineering solutions at the conceptual design stage (Holzner, Downing 2010). The effectiveness of decisions, defined as the relation between the impact of the decision on the final building performance and the cost of the action needed to implement the decision, declines during the various stages of the life of a building. The decisions made early have the greatest impact on the performance and the efficiency of a building for its entire life, while the cost is often minimal (Heiselberg 2007), see Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Effectiveness of decisions made in different stages of a buildings lifetime (Heiselberg 2007).

Today, the construction industry is in the early stages of a revolution to reinvent the design process (Heiselberg 2007). All ready at the beginning of projects design teams include both architects and

engineers and the building design is transferred into an iterative collaborative process from the conceptual design ideas to the final detailed design, see Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Integrated design process (Heiselberg 2007).

The integrated design approach achieves this improved energy utilization and an improvement in the environmental performance of the building due to the relationship that exists between the building, its architecture and engineering (Heiselberg 2007).

SPECIFIC FOCUSS

A lack of innovative designs in the Dutch Building industry can be observed for roofs. At the moment the cooperation between architects and roofers is lacking and as a result there are often problems with leaking roofs of buildings.

Sub-optimal interaction and cooperation between solutions and construction in design practice of roofs is presented by professional parties as main cause of the lack of innovative roofs (EURACTIVE ROOF-er 2005). During the design process, teams generate new knowledge by exchange and develop information about the design to be produced. Such a design process for the design of a (new) product is called a Collaborative Design (Bento et al. 2004). Within such a setting, actors like Architects and Roofers, differ in cultural backgrounds, their way of working, and have a different motivation of collaboration (Korbijn 1999). Architect and Roofer collaborating on the roof design, acting as representatives of their discipline can be described and defined by their Competence Profiles which is expressed in their design activities as Dorst (1997) explains. Due to interdependency

between the participants (Latour 1987) knowledge exchange and sharing is needed by their interpersonal communication and using preferred communication tools (Emmitt et al. 2008).

METHODOLOGY

To identify the various types of knowledge of Architects and Roofers it is necessary to define more specific typologies of knowledge. Van Aken (2005) discriminates process-, object- and realization-knowledge as part of the design-knowledge. The process knowledge will link the needed requirements for designs (object knowledge) and the possible physical solutions (realization knowledge) (van Aken 2005). Van Aken (2005) distinct between object-knowledge related to designers (Architects), and realization-knowledge related to contractors (Roofers). The types of knowledge stated, are communicated between Architect and Roofer (both having another educational background, level of abstract thinking and a such differ largely in competences and skills) through different kinds of representation (Brereton 1998). Related to the type of knowledge and the team-collaboration between architect and roofer the focus will be on explicit ‘object and realization knowledge’ (van Aken 2005). This focus generates the information which makes clear how the contribution of the discipline based object knowledge and realization knowledge is communicated and how this knowledge is transformed into the design concepts. Based on this the research focus on the possibility to support the exchange of the different types of knowledge with a tool, see fig. 3.

Figure 3. Typology of knowledge and role design support tool

Our focus is only on explicit design knowledge because this knowledge is expressed or notated in a way that it can be administrated and communicated

within the team and with other participants, such as advisors and clients, during the process. The building design activities, classified as both rational (Simon 1973) and reflective (Schön 1987), for structuring and develop the object- and realization-knowledge, are identified through the use of the Morphological Overviews (Savanovic 2009).

Our research with workshops - learning by doing - for Design Teams in practice with professionals, both for development and evaluation, is ongoing from the year 2000 through the study Integral Design (Quanjel & Zeiler 2003). A new research started by Savanović (2009) in 2004 sets the methodological basis for the knowledge based research in a Collaborative Team-setting. Related to the type of research - technological design - an appropriate methodology is necessary to design the setting as well as the analysing methods needed. The main theoretical knowledge used are the Methodical Design model (Van den Kroonenberg and Siers, 1992) and the Design Research Methodology (Blessing and Chakrabarti 2009). With the help of Design Research Methodology a framework was used to developed the Design Model of Methodical Design (Zeiler, 1993) into the Integral Design-method, executed through workshops and the use of a specific support tool - Morphological Overviews (Savanovic 2009). The morphological Overviews pay an essential role in the design process representing a set of necessary conditions for the creation of integral design concepts for design teams with equal educational background. The Morphological Overviews are used to introduce, discuss and structure the different kinds of knowledge (object- and realization knowledge) of the participants in order to generate more optimal or new design solutions. In this research the focus is on the stimulation of knowledge exchange between Architects and Roofers / Installers in the setting of Collaborative Design (Collaborative Design Workshops), and the influence of a structuring support tool (Morphological Overviews) on knowledge exchange and its effects on the number of studied functions and generated solutions. The design tool was tested in workshops.

Until now we had two pre-workshops with in total about 45 students (Quanjel et al 2007), four pre-workshops with in total 55 professionals (Architects, Roofers and Installers)(Quanjel and Zeiler 2009).

After these primarily experiments two final Collaborative Design Workshops series were held in which in total 48 professional (Architects, Roofers and Installers) participated.

The methodology used for the development of the Collaborative Design Workshops is comparable to a design of this setting with iterative design steps related to analysis, selecting and shaping the set-up of the workshops. The results of the previous workshop led to the requirements of the next workshop. To describe the development of the model for the Collaborative Design Workshop we use for each step in this development five criteria; the characteristics of the method to train participants in a Collaborative Design-setting. These criteria are; aim or outline, steps within the development, evaluation, communication and testing. At the end of each workshops there was an evaluation part; the participants / design teams could present and discuss their designs, the collaboration related to the workshop setup and the use of the design method. Through a predefined questionnaire the participants could reflect on the set up of the workshop and the introduced support tool (Morphological Overviews). The experiments (Yin 1994), 'workshops' were held with professionals of the different involved disciplines designers and roofer engineers, with focus on the following aspects:

- communication between the design- and engineering solutions for active roofs
- generation of more possible design / engineering solutions for active roofs
- the use of the support decision tool to generate these design / engineering solutions

The experiments have the format of design task workshops and/or master classes related to design tasks. As example, related to the setting of workshops and the use of ID tools we can define the following functionalities / needs related to these experiments:

- situation of the design-team without the use of methodical design tools
- situation of design team by using methodical design tools

To distinguish the knowledge-exchange aspects related to the use of the tools of ID, several views are used to extract data out of design teams: by evaluation-questionnaires for all participants,

photographs of the produced items by the team and video-registration / analysis of the experiments.

EXPERIMENTAL WORKSHOPS

The set-up of the workshops included aspects related to the organisation, location, program with time-schedule and design-tasks. The type of monitors and type monitoring are related to the requirement monitoring and analysing methods. These aspects are addressed separately in another parallel paper. The methodology used for this development is comparable to a design of this setting with iterative design steps related to analysis, selecting and shaping the set-up of the workshops. The results of the previous workshop led to the requirements of the next workshop. To describe each step of the development of the model for the Collaborative Design Workshop five criteria were used;

- aim or outline,
- steps within the development,
- evaluation,
- communication
- testing. First a brief description of these criteria.

The aim and outline for each step in the development has to be described before executing this step; each step has the outline of a workshop. The aim should cover each time the criteria which are necessary to function as a method. This defines the next characteristic; the method should have clear steps to be taken to develop and execute. Through evaluation of each step, related to the criteria, the definition of the next step(s) or aim(s) is generated. A method can only be defined as such if the execution of this method can be communicated in such a way that other competent individuals or organizations can execute the method in the same way as it was developed and used by the researcher. This makes the method able to test the specific aims in the specific context. Aspects of time; is the organisation of the method time-consuming, and functionality; is the method easy and to use in the correct way, are related to testing the method. At the end of each workshops there was an evaluation part; the participants / design teams could present and discuss their designs, the collaboration related to the workshop setup and the use of the design method. Through a predefined questionnaire the

participants could reflect on the set up of the workshop and the introduced support tool (Morphological Overviews). Six month after the workshop was held a second identical questionnaire was sent to the participants to get a better insight in the impact of the workshop and design method into practice. All participants could submit freely to the workshops with the restriction of 10 years of practical experience, all architects are member of the BNA, all roofers are member of the Roofer Organization Het Hellend Dak or Vebidak. Through coupling with the competence profiles, the relations with the 'theoretically present specific knowledge (object- or realization knowledge) and the type of professional (Architect or Roofer) can be identified. The workshops were announced as workshops for Integral Design for Innovative Roofs organized by the BNA and the Roofer Organizations in collaboration with the Technische Universiteit Eindhoven.

FINAL WORKSHOP SERIES

First the final workshop-setting as a model is described, than the criteria of the model are explained and discussed. The goal of the Collaborative Design Workshop is to train professional Architects, Roofers and Installers in Collaborative Design. The Collaborative Design Workshop is to be used in the preliminary phase of the design. The workshop introduces a Collaborative Design-setting and a specific design tool - Morphological Overviews - for supporting professionals with different educational background in organizing the design process and the knowledge needed for this design process from the different participants. The final product of the Collaborative Design Workshop is that the process approach as well as the Morphological Overviews are accepted as such and experienced by the participants as positive contribution to their practice in collaboration and design.

First step is to come to a coherent program, amount and type of participants and a location. The program should contain introduction of the support tools by the researcher, lectures by experts for state of the art, use and innovation related to sustainable energy systems on roofs. All design tasks are comparable in difficulty and time-schedule (1 hour). The program contains a structure of collaboration steps and

learning steps. By starting individually the traditional setting is experienced. After that the participants are split up in teams, Architect-Roofer or Architect-Installer, to work on a second comparable design task. One group starts immediately with this task. The other group of teams gets first an introduction of the support tool MO and continues afterwards with the same design task. The first group will get this introduction after they have finished their design-task. At the end of the first day the different experiences are discussed with the different groups related to the workshop-setting and the use of the Morphological Overview. There should be at least one week between the first workshop-day and the second-day to give room to reflection on the first experiences. The second day starts with a short summary of the first day. Changed teams work, after a third lecture and introduction of the task on a third design-question. One group will work for the second time with the support tool, the other group for the first time. After this task again there is a discussion with the teams about the workshop-setting and the use of the support-tool. After a fourth lecture and design-task introduction, the last design task is a more free design task where changed teams are working together, they are also free to use the Morphological Overviews. The final part of the workshop is a final evaluation, fill in of the questionnaires and a more informal part with a drink.

There is a strict Competence Profile for the participants: At least 10 years of process and project-knowledge / experience. These Competence Profiles are available through the Professional Vocational-Organisations. The Competence Profiles are the basis of the specific knowledge each specific profession has with a certain experience. To be able to work each time in a different team-setting at least 6 Architects and 3 Roofers and Installers are needed for each workshop-setting.

The following criteria are set to the different goals:

- Participants: positive results of all questions of the predefined questionnaire format used for immediately after the workshop and 6 month after the workshop, combined

with the evaluation sessions after each design-task.

- Professional organisations (Architects, Roofers, Installers): positive practical use of the workshop-script related to program, participants and location as well as time-consumption and financial aspects.

Two final experiments with this setting were done, in June and November 2009, see for the set-up of the final workshops series Fig. 4. The workshop-setting was evaluated with the professional participants. To give the participants, as part of the learning cycle, time to reflect on the use of the Morphological Overviews and the Workshop-setting (Fig. 6) the workshop is divided in two parts; there is one week between the first part (design task 1 and design task 2) and second part (design task 3). For generalization of the results parallel to the setting the workshop-setting incorporates teams with Architect and Roofer, as well as Architect and Installer. First part of the workshop has two steps; step one working individually without the support tool, this to get insight in the specific discipline knowledge related to the Competence Profiles and found functions, aspects and solutions. The second step implied the working in teams (design task 2) parallel with and without Morphological Overviews (MO). After one week the same participants come together. Now the teams are changed so that there is no influence on the group-learning process. Changed teams formally working with Morphological Overviews (MO) are now working for the second time with the Morphological Overviews. Changed teams from the other group which were not working yet with the Morphological Overviews are now working for the first time with this design support tool. Explicit Design knowledge can be compared as well within this step as with step 2. Using the second-loop-learning effects method as Argyris (1999) described, the changed teams are working all for the second time with Morphological Overviews as a support tool and can reflect on this as well as on the workshop-setting itself. Due to the parallel design-sessions in separate rooms comparison of the monitoring situation is optimized.

steps			focus
design task 1 - functionalities and solutions	Architects individual <i>without</i> tool	functionalities and solutions Individual <i>without</i> tool registration (analyzing phase)	
design task 2 - functionalities and solutions > design	 team <i>without</i> tool (MO)	Functionalities, solutions + design team <i>with</i> / <i>without</i> tool registration + observation (synthesizing phase)	
design task 3 - feed-back > design - team <i>with</i> tool (MO) -presentation / evaluation	 team <i>with</i> tool (MO)	functionalities and solutions team <i>with</i> tool registration + observation (learning effect)+ questionnaire (synthesizing phase)	

Figure 4. Overview of the steps of the final workshop series model.

RESULTS

The evaluation of workshops series by the participants was done through applying a predefined format questionnaire, as used in all former workshops, see table 1. For comparison the results of a similar evaluation about the workshops for

professionals with the same educational background from the research of Savanovic (2009) are given in the last row of table 1.

The effect of the use of morphological overviews on the generated number of functions and solutions by the design teams is represented in Fig. 5.

Table 1. Overview of average ratings questionnaire-format on a scale from 1(lowestrating) to 10 (highest rating) for the final series Collaborative Design Workshops, direct after the workshops. Also the results from Savanovic 2009 for comparison

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
A = Architect / R = Roofer / I = Installer	How important use MO to your practice	What rate for the Workshop set-up	Use of MO - general	Usefull to stimulate use MO within practice	Expectation future use of MO
Rating 1-5					
A average	6,2	7,6	6,6	6,8	5,8
R average	5,6	8,0	6,6	7,6	6,6
I average	5,6	6,0	6,0	6,6	6,6
Total average	5,9	7,3	6,5	7,0	6,2
<i>Total average research Savanovic (2009) series 5</i>	7,5	7,6	8,0	8,2	7,2

Figure 5. The effect of applying Morphological Overviews on the average amount of generated functions and solutions

EVALUATION RESULTS

The architects and roofers were more positive about the use of Morphological Overviews than installers, see table 1. All participants thought the importance of use of Morphological Overviews to their practice relative low, with the architects the most positive with a average rating of 6,2. In contrast however the architects had the lowest rating for their expectation of future use of Morphological Overviews. The workshop set-up was evaluated most positive. So clearly the rather low rating for the aspects connected to the Morphological Overviews was not caused by the preparation of the workshop. Compared with the results of the questionnaires from the research of Savanovic (2009) it clearly shows that the application of Morphological Overviews in this context was appreciated significantly less. This might be an indication that the rather abstract approach was something the participants were not used to work with, in their daily practice.

Comparing the individual results by the architects, roofers and installers in session 1, to the design teams without Morphological Overviews in session 2, there was a clear increase in the number of functions generated but a slight decrease of the number of generated solutions. Comparing the design sessions in which the design teams apply the Morphological Overviews there was an increase in the number of generated functions as well as a significant increase of the number of generated solutions.

DISCUSSION

The difference between the builders and the designers in working with and appreciating the Morphological Overviews might lay in their educational background and way of designing. The architects design in a more iterative way and less linear structured way than the builders (roofers/installers). For the architects it is more obvious to work with an associative way of collecting and developing different aspects and solutions related to the design task, especially at the beginning of the design. Builders are forced to work more restricted because realizing and constructing the design means a precise organization of aspects and solutions to come to realization.

Although the number of participants in the workshops was rather small (17 participating architects, 8 roofers and 9 installers), it was not realistic to apply all kind of statistical analysis to the results. Still we think because they were real experienced participants and because it was in a setting supported by the professional organizations, the results have real meaning for practice. Within a wider range of the 6th framework Pan-European project the setting of workshops was used for developing the Methodical Design Tools training-set up by the several Collaborative Design team-members for the Active Roof Design (EUR-ACTIVE ROOFer 2005). This project was aimed at the development of a methodology for supporting not only the architect but the whole design team in the early phase of the design process on integrating active roofs (roofs as energy generating integrated

building components) as part of the product development.

Based on the found and verified functionalities / needs a supportive overview can be generated as part of the developed Integral Design methodology by using morphological overviews. Through the use of this tool more insight in the knowledge exchange between different design team members can be generated. Requirements as specified with the help of the support tool will become clear and can be modified when the circumstances change.

CONCLUSIONS

Our research with workshops - learning by doing - for Building Design Teams in practice with professionals, both for development and evaluation, is ongoing from the year 2000 through the study Integral Design (Quanjel & Zeiler 2003). The research started by Savanović in 2004 (Savanović 2009) set the methodological basis for the knowledge based research in a Collaborative Team-setting. Complementary to the research of Savanović (2009), concerning teams with participants with the same educational background, the research related to this paper views Collaborative Design focusing on roofs, where there is a large difference between the educational level of architects compared to that of roofers and installers. To improve the roof design a supportive process approach that stimulates collaboration between Architect and Roofer was developed and tested. The research for the Collaborative Team setting is strongly related to the problems and needs from practice. All participants were positive about the influence of the use of the Morphological Overviews related to improvement of communication and design process; the explicit way of discussing, notating and developing the aspects and solutions could be addressed as the main reason.

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